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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE STUDENTS' PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ADOPTED BY PRINCIPALS FOR ADMINISTRATION OF PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ABIA STATE

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Abstract

This researcher investigated the students' personnel management practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 16,033 respondents made up of 254 principals and 10,939 SS 2 students of public secondary schools and 727 principals and 4,113 SS 2 students of private secondary schools in Abia State. The sample for the study was 853 respondents drawn using proportionate random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a researcher-developed questionnaire titled "Principals' Student Personnel Management Practices for School Administration Rating Scale (PSPMPSARS)". The instrument was subjected to face validation by five experts made up of three experts in Educational Management and Planning as well as the two experts in Measurement and Evaluation. Cronbach Alpha which was used for test of the internal consistency of the instrument yielded overall coefficient of 0.84. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed among others that deliberation on the requirements for admission, advertising the sale of admission forms, reviewing the qualifications of applicants, shortlisting and conducting entrance examinations for eligible applicants, offer admission to candidates who successfully pass entrance examinations, register and placement of successful candidates in classes were the admission practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State. It was also found out that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the guidance and counselling practices they adopt. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that State Ministry of Education should develop admission handbook and distribute to principals to guide them in applying admission practices to maintain standard and uniformity in selecting students to be admitted in secondary schools in the study.

Keywords

Students Personnel, Practices, Principals, School Administration, Admission, Guidance and Counselling.

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Introduction

Education is an instrument for improving knowledge, talents, potentials and skills of individuals towards enabling them contribute to sustained improvement of personal wellbeing in particular and development of the society at large. It equally enables individuals to develop critical thinking ability personal values for purposeful living in the society and appreciate/cultivate dignity of labour. Ezinine and Okekeocha (2021) opined that education is an indispensable tool for developing individuals' skills and knowledge which enables them become self-reliant, creative and innovative in venturing into industrial, political, social and economic activities of the society.

Education helps individuals to learn and exhibit desirable behaviour in the society. Onye, Odionye and Ihemmeje (2016) opined that education is a means of acquiring knowledge, skills, attitude and societal norms by people to transmit to the next generation for meaningful development of the society. In Nigeria, education is categorized into various levels namely: pre-primary education, basic education, secondary education and tertiary education. The concern of this study is secondary education.

Secondary education enables students to acquire requisite knowledge, sound ideas and fundamental skills to further their education at higher level. According to Nwafor and Robert-Okah (2022), secondary education provides an opportunity for primary school leavers to acquire more skills, built on already gained knowledge and develop abilities that prepare them to live effectively in the changing society full of opportunities. Secondary education is the second tier of education that serves as the bridge between primary and the tertiary levels of education. According to Nwanga and Unachukwu (2021), secondary education which is received after primary education and before tertiary education enables students acquires fundamental knowledge and veritable skills for higher education and useful living in the society. Onyeukwu (2022) opined that secondary education equips its recipients with moral integrity, intellectual honesty, respect for persons, compassion and courage and above all capacity, to live a righteous life. Secondary education inculcates tolerance, kindness diligence and respect for dignity of labour in individuals. Ubido and Okorji (2021) stressed that the secondary education shapes characters of learners and widens their knowledge of various subjects which prepare them for further studies in higher institutions of learning. There are two categories of secondary schools namely public or private secondary schools.

Public secondary schools are owned, controlled and managed by government, while the private secondary schools are owned, controlled and managed by individuals, groups or non-governmental organization. Nwanga and Unachukwu (2021) noted that public secondary schools are established, funded and managed by the government, while private secondary schools are established, funded and managed by individuals, groups or mission bodies. Similar to this, Nwogbo and Ilavbare (2021) asserted that the public secondary schools are owned, financed and controlled by the government, private secondary schools are owned, financed and controlled by individuals, missionary bodies and non-government organization among others. Ilavbare and Nwogbo (2021) asserted that the public secondary schools were financed by with taxpayer's money to provide equal education opportunities to the masses irrespective of their tribes, religion economic or political status, while private secondary school are owned and managed by individuals, private groups and organizations to educate students and make profit. The manager of either public or private secondary school is the principal.

The principal is the chief executive officer charged with daily operation of a secondary school. Okeke and Ikediugwu (2020) noted that it is the duty of a principal as the chief executive to

plan, organize, direct and control the day-to-day activities of the school to accomplish education goals through utilizing the available resources. The principal as the chief administrator is responsible for overseeing the daily operations of a secondary school. Ohamobi, Akulue and Okonkwo (2021) asserted that principals as the chief administrator of secondary school level of education are entrusted with many responsibilities such as developing standardized curricula, assessing teaching methods, monitoring students' achievement, encourage parents involvement in school, revise policies and procedures, administer the budget, hire and evaluate staff and oversee facilities. The principal as the leader is responsible for the daily administration of secondary school.

School administration is the process of planning, directing, controlling and managing the affairs of an institution of learning. Okeke and Ikediugwu (2020) defined school administration is the managerial tasks that are concerned with the attainment of set objectives through the utilization of the available resources in secondary schools. It is a social process concerned with getting things done by motivating and controlling the activities of others. Ikuelogbon and Ikuelogbon (2021) defined school administration as the process of skillfully arranging and utilizing the available human and material resources for achieving educational objectives. Operationally, administration is a set of activities directing at ensuring judicious use of the available resources to attain set objectives of an education institution. One of the crucial administrative functions of principal is the students' personnel management.

Student personnel management has been conceptualized by different authors. According to Ohamobi, Akulue and Okonkwo (2021), students personnel management is all the activities that are carried out by the school administrator to ensure that the students derive the best from the school curricular and extracurricular activities. It is concerned with the controlling, organizing and directing the affairs of learners in the school organization. Nwanga, Amaikwu and Ugwo (2021) defined students' personnel management as the act of planning and controlling the activities and behaviour of students for healthy and stimulating learning environment that promote their mental stability, physical fitness and academic excellent. Operationally, students personnel management as the services or activities carried out by school administrator to manage and control the learners to enable them derive the best from the school programmes. The school administrators can effectively control and coordinate learners through applying students' personnel management practices.

There are various students' personnel management practices in the school system. These practices identified by Akpan (2016) included; guidance and counseling services, orientation programmes, discipline, sports, health and safety services. Similar to this, Mbon and Okoi (2019) noted that personnel management practices include admission exercise, orientation, accommodation, medical services, library services, students; academic records, guidance and counseling, financial services, security services, co-curricular activities among others. This study focused on admission practices and guidance and counselling practices.

Admission is the process of selecting eligible candidates for entrance to study in institutions of learning. Okpa, Alade, Odigwe and Sule (2020) defined admission as the formal process of accepting students into the school or a programme of choice having met the prescribed requirements. Admission is the process of selecting students for entrance or study into institution of learning. Yusuf, Zahyah and Muhajir (2019) asserted that admission is a systematic process of admitting qualified students who had satisfied the entrance requirements designed by the school. The author asserted that it is the services that school offer to prospective applicants who want to be enrolled. It is the responsibility of school administrators to admit students in schools. The school administrators evaluate the eligibility of the applicants for acceptance to study in schools through admission

practices. Admission practice is the pattern and procedure for selecting the students to study in educational institution. Nwanga, Amaikwu and Ugwo (2021) stressed that admission practices entail identifying the number of students needed in the school based on the available facilities, devising of requirement, advertising and sales of from, review of applications, conducting tests and selecting the eligible candidates. The candidates successful admitted to study in secondary school are exposed to orientation to enable them adjust to the school culture.

Guidance and counselling is a programme or activity that is geared toward assisting the students to solve their social, educational and vocational programmes. According to Usman, Ahmed and Rizwana (2021), guidance and counselling a process of assisting individuals to understand themselves and solve educational, personal, social, mental, emotional and Career or vocational problems. Guidance and counselling service helps students to cope with school life, make career choice and subject combinations to pursue it. Ebuk and Owan (2020) noted that guidance and counselling helps the students to acquire skills and competences in different areas of their studies to handle academic matters, cope with social personal needs,/relationships, life and function maximally in different vocation or occupation of choice. Similar to this, Ohamobi, Akulue and Okonkwo (2021) pointed out that guidance and counselling also help students to identify the various career options based on their interest, values and attitudes as well as possible opportunities in the labour market and also to use this information in career planning and course selection. In a school, the guidance and counselling programme assists students in harmonizing their abilities, interests and values and enables them to develop their full potential (Abdulwahab&Galamaji, 2021). Guidance and counselling helps students to realize their abilities, interest, environment, personality and how learn best to adjust them in order to succeed in their studies.

The personal observation of the researcher informed that there are multiple cases of misconducts among students in most secondary schools in Abia State. These misconducts include sneaking out from the school premises during instructional period, dressing indecently to school, speaking vernacular during teaching and learning process, making noise in the classroom, engaging in fighting, examination malpractice and drugs. The researcher also observed the cases of immoral act, lateness to school, absenteeism, bullying, disrespect of constituted authority and destruction of school property. A further investigation by the researcher revealed that these cases of misconducts may be attributed to poor students' personnel management. The researcher also experienced cases of bullying, lateness, absenteeism and disruptive behaviour of students in classroom which may be connected to failure of the principals to effectively apply students' personnel management practices in secondary schools in Abia State.

The misbehaviours of students have prevented them from deriving maximum benefits from secondary school programmes in Abia State. The scenarios of misconducts among learners have made students' personnel management practices a pressing issue. These states of unpleasant affairs could be connected to insensitivity and failure of principals to manage the students' personnel. It is against this backdrop that the researcher analyzed the students' personnel management practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State.

Statement of the Problem

The basic function of the school principals is to facilitate intellectual, moral, physical, emotional and social development of students. The principals ensure that students are properly educated in a conducive learning environment through the application of students' personnel management practices such as admission exercise, as well as guidance and counseling services. This may account for absenteeism, bullying, examination malpractices, cultism, lateness to school and

moral laxity among others. The students' misbehavior probably are due to inadequate orientation programme to enlighten them of the dos and don'ts of schools, failure to apply school rules to guide their conduct and limited access to guidance and counselling services to shape their behaviour. The appears to be preferential treatment in favour of less qualified candidates with connections during admission processes in public and private secondary schools in Abia State. It is based on the problem that the study analyzed the students' personnel management practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to carry out a comparative study of the students' personnel management practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State. Specifically, the study sought to compare:

1. admission practice adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State.
2. guidance and counselling practice adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the admission practice adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State?
2. What are the guidance and counselling practice adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the admission practices they adopt.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the guidance and counselling practices they adopt.

Method

Survey research design was adopted for the study. According to Sharma, Jha, Koirala, Aryal and Bhattarai (2023), survey research design is the one that involves collection and analysis of data to describe the characteristics or opinions of a population or a phenomenon by studying a sample. This design is deemed appropriate for the study, since the researcher collected data that described the opinions of the given sample of the population on the students' personnel management practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State. The study was carried out in Abia State in southeast, Nigeria. The choice of Abia State as the area of the study is due to the fact that misbehavior of students which could be attributed to improper students' personnel management practices.

The population of the study comprised 16,033 respondents made up of 254 principals and 10,939 SS 2 students of public secondary schools and 727 principals and 8,113 SS 2 students of private secondary schools in Abia State. The sample for the study was 853 respondents made up of 27 principals and 547 SS 2 students of public and 72 principals and 207 SS 2 students of private

secondary schools drawn using proportionate random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a researcher-developed questionnaire titled “Principals’ Student Personnel Management Practices for School Administration Questionnaire Rating Scale (PSPMPAQRS)”. The instrument was developed based on literature review and consultation of experts in the field of education. The instrument has two sections namely, A and B. Section “A” deal with the demographic variable of the respondents such as school types, while section B contains Clusters I to II which elicit information concerning student personnel management practices for school administration. These parts were based on the two areas of students’ personnel management practices adopted in this study. Cluster I which is concerned with admission practices for school administration has eleven items and cluster II contained eleven items on guidance and counselling practices. The instrument contains 22 items structured on a four-point likert-type scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D); Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The face validation of the instruments were determined by five specialists, three from the Department of Management and Planning, and two from Department of Measurement and Evaluation, all from Faculty of Education, Imo State University, Owerri. The researcher presented the title, purpose of the study, research questions, hypotheses and the copies of the instruments to five experts and requested them to examine and scrutinize the items in terms of contents, relevance, suitability, clarity and coverage of the dimensions of the study. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through Cronbach alpha which yielded coefficient values of 0.84 and 0.84 were obtained for Clusters I and II of instrument with overall reliability coefficient value of 0.84.

The researcher with the help of four research assistants who are secondary school teachers in Abia State used direct approach for data collection. A total of 853 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 827 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 97% return rate. The instrument that was properly filled and successfully retrieved were used for data analysis. The data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation for answering the research questions and t-test for testing the hypotheses. The decision rule for the research questions is that mean ratings of 2.50 and above was taken as agreement and any mean rating that falls below 2.50 was taken to indicate disagreement. In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, where p-value is equal to or greater than level of significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted but where p-value is less than level of significant value of 0.05, the null hypotheses was rejected.

Results

Research Question One: What are the admission practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State?

Table 1: Analysis of Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on admission practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State.

S/N	ITEMS	Public schools (N =559)			Private Schools (N =268)		
		$\bar{x}$	SD	Decision	$\bar{x}$	SD	Decision
	The principal adopts the underlisted admission practices for school administration						
1	Deliberating on the requirements for admission into the school	2.69	1.10	Agree	2.73	1.17	Agree
2	Advertising the sale of admission forms to members of the public through various media	2.69	1.09	Agree	2.71	1.12	Agree
3	Reviewing the qualifications of applicants for admission	2.45	.94	Agree	2.59	1.14	Agree

4	Shortlisting eligible applicants for entrance examinations	2.60	1.14	Agree	2.57	1.14	Agree
5	Conduct entrance examinations for candidates who purchase the admission forms	2.61	1.10	Agree	2.57	1.14	Agree
6	Invite successful candidates in the entrance examinations for oral interview	2.45	1.10	Disagree	2.32	1.07	Disagree
7	Offer admission to candidates who successfully pass entrance examinations	2.71	1.07	Agree	2.56	1.17	Agree
8	Instruct candidates who are admitted to submit their credentials for screening	2.61	1.13	Agree	2.68	1.11	Agree
9	Provide instruction on how to make necessary payments to candidates	2.57	1.11	Agree	2.58	1.11	Agree
10	Register candidates who have made the necessary payments	2.63	1.19	Agree	2.60	1.08	Agree
11	Place successful candidates in various classes based on entrance examination performance	2.69	1.15	Agree	2.72	1.14	Agree
Mean of Means		2.61	1.10	Agree	2.60	1.13	Agree

The table 1 contains the respondents' mean ratings of the admission practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State. The respondents both in public and private secondary schools have mean scores above the cut off mean of 2.50 for all items except item 6 which indicate agreement with the statements as admission practices adopted by principals for administration of secondary schools.

The average standard deviation scores of 1.10 and 1.13 for respondents in public and private secondary schools respectively shows that their responses are close and this indicates homogeneity in their responses. The mean of means of 2.61 and 2.60 for the respondents in public and private secondary school respectively which are above 2.50 indicated principals adopt admission practices for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State. The admission practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State included: deliberating on the requirements for admission into the school, advertising the sale of admission forms, reviewing the qualifications of applicants for admission, shortlisting and conducting entrance examinations for eligible applicants, offer admission to candidates who successfully pass entrance examinations, register and placement of successful candidates in classes.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the admission practices they adopt.

Table 2: Analysis of Independent t-test of no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the admission practices they adopt

Respondents	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	p-value	Df	∞	Remark
Public Schools	559	2.61	1.10	0.94	825	0.05	Not Significant
Private Schools	268	2.60	1.13				

Data presented on Table 2 revealed that the p-value of 0.94 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance at 825 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the admission practices they adopt.

Research Question Two: What are the guidance and counselling practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State?

Table 3: Analysis of Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on guidance and counselling adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State

S/N	ITEMS	Public schools (N =559)			Private Schools (N =268)		
		$\bar{x}$	SD	Decision	$\bar{x}$	SD	Decision
	The principal adopts the underlisted guidance and counselling practices for school administration						
12	Collaborating with the school counsellor to help students overcome challenges that interfere with their studies	2.75	1.05	Agree	2.73	1.18	Agree
13	Organising interactive session to guide students on various ways of overcoming their academic problem	2.79	.98	Agree	2.55	1.11	Agree
14	Initiate follow-up to monitor the progress of students exposed to counselling	2.51	1.13	Agree	2.50	1.19	Agree
15	Refers students' cases that are beyond professional abilities of school staff to appropriate expert to handle	2.44	1.08	Disagree	2.41	1.08	Disagree
16	Honours all promises made to students before counselling exercise	2.38	1.12	Disagree	2.24	1.17	Disagree
17	Working with the school counsellor to handle students with deviant behaviours	2.65	1.08	Agree	2.62	1.16	Agree
18	Listing the relevant subjects required for various career	2.63	1.11	Agree	2.60	1.16	Agree
19	Placing students in classes based on their career interest and abilities	2.57	1.16	Agree	2.58	1.15	Agree
20	Offering assistance to students at intervals on how to overcome their academic problems	2.65	1.11	Agree	2.63	1.22	Agree
21	Providing information on professional requirements for various jobs and careers	2.69	1.11	Agree	2.58	1.22	Agree
22	Inviting professional to give talks to guide the students in their choice of career and academic development	2.63	1.10	Agree	2.56	1.15	Agree
	Mean of Means	2.61	1.09	Agree	2.55	1.16	Agree

Table 3 shows the mean ratings on the guidance and counselling practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State. The mean scores for respondents in public and private secondary schools for items 12, 13, 14, and 17-22 are higher than the criterion mean value of 2.50 and this indicates agreement with these items as their guidance and counselling practices. The results further reveal that respondents in public and private secondary schools disagreed with items 15 and 16, as their guidance and counselling practices.

The cluster standard deviation scores of respondents in public and private secondary schools are 1.09 and 1.16 respectively and this indicates that there is homogeneity amongst their responses indicating a similar consensus of opinion. The mean of means of 2.61 and 2.55 for respondents in public and private secondary schools respectively which are above 2.50 indicated agreement that the listed guidance and counselling practices are adopted by principals. This indicated that are the collaborating with the school counsellor to help students overcome challenges that interfere with their studies, organising interactive session to guide students on various ways of overcoming their academic problem, initiate follow-up to monitor the progress of students exposed to counselling, working with the school counsellor to handle students with deviant behaviours, listing the

relevant subjects required for various career, offering assistance to students at intervals on how to overcome their academic problems, providing information on professional requirements for various jobs and careers and inviting professional to give talks to guide the students in their choice of career and academic development are the guidance and counselling practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State.

Hypothesis Four

There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the guidance and counselling practices they adopt.

Table 4: Analysis of Independent t-test of no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the guidance and counselling practices they adopt

Respondents	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	p-value	Df	α	Remark
Public Schools	559	2.61	1.09	0.44	825	0.05	Not Significant
Private Schools	268	2.55	1.16				

Results in Table 4, shows that the p-value of 0.44 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance at 825 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the guidance and counselling practices they adopt.

Discussion of the Findings

The results of the study indicated that the admission practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State included: deliberating on the requirements for admission into the school, advertising the sale of admission forms, reviewing the qualifications of applicants for admission, shortlisting and conducting entrance examinations for eligible applicants, offer admission to candidates who successfully pass entrance examinations, register and placement of successful candidates in classes. This is in line with the finding of Nwanga, Amaikwu and Ugwo (2021) which indicated that the admission practices are applied by principals in the administration of public and private secondary schools in Ebonyi State include devising admission requirements into school, advertise the sale of admission forms through mass media, sales of application forms to members of the public, review of applications from members of the public, conduct entrance examinations for students, screen students' credentials for possible admission and offer admission to eligible candidates. The possible explanation for the agreement is due to the fact that the two studies were conducted in south-east, where similar policy is used in admission and school administration. The admission practices are probably adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State to ensure that the most eligible candidates are admitted. The admission practices adopted by principals deliberately promote and maintain academic standard and excellence in secondary education in Abia State which could account for outstanding academic achievement of students in external examinations in the state. Further result revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the admission practices they adopt. This also supported the finding of Nwanga, Amaikwu and Ugwo (2021) which indicated that there was no significant in the admission practices applied by public and private secondary school principals in school administration. The agreement in

findings could be attributed to similarity in geographical locations of the studies, and the period in which the two studies were carried out.

The findings of the study showed that collaborating with the school counsellor to help students overcome challenges that interfere with their studies, organising interactive session to guide students on various ways of overcoming their academic problem, initiate follow-up to monitor the progress of students exposed to counselling, working with the school counsellor to handle students with deviant behaviours, listing the relevant subjects required for various career, offering assistance to students at intervals on how to overcome their academic problems, providing information on professional requirements for various jobs and careers and inviting professional to give talks to guide the students in their choice of career and academic development are the guidance and counselling practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State. This agreed with the finding of Kazimoto (2022) indicated that similar guidance and counselling services are rendered by principals in public and private secondary schools. This also supported the finding of Egenti (2020) which indicated counselling strategies utilized by principals of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State were ensuring that students have individuals or group counselling session, collaborating with counsellor and confronting the problems of students with the help of school counsellors. The two studies were conducted in eastern part of Nigeria and this could account for agreement between the findings. The guidance and counselling practices adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State provide necessary information to students to increase their self-awareness and handle their academic and personal problems which contribute to their academic, emotional and social development. The students of public and private secondary exposed to guidance and counselling probably understand their abilities, aptitudes and interest which assist them to develop their potentials in the school. Further result revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of public and private secondary school principals and students on the guidance and counselling practices they adopt. This is in line with the finding of Egenti (2020) which indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of guidance and counselling strategies utilized by principals of public and private secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in agreement with the finding of Kazimoto (2022) indicated that there is no significant difference in the guidance and counselling services are rendered by principals in public and private secondary schools. The possible explanation for the finding is that the principals of public and private secondary schools probably understand that guidance and counselling enable students to understand their traits and personality which guide them in developing their academic and vocational plans.

Conclusion

It is concluded that similar students' personnel management were adopted by principals for administration of public and private secondary schools in Abia State. These students' personnel management practices were admission and guidance and counselling to ensure students not only derive maximum benefits from educational programmes but also attain high academic achievement which is recorded by students in external examination in Abia State. The students' personnel management practices adopted by principals also implies that learners receive medical attentions, necessary information and guidance to help them excel in their academic pursuit and make the right career choice in secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. State Ministry of Education should develop admission handbook and make available for principals to serve as guideline for applying admission practices to maintain standard and uniformity in selecting students to be admitted in secondary schools in the study.
2. There is need for sustained improvement in principals' provision of health support services to students through appeal to non-government and wealthy individuals for funds to regularly conduct medical test for students and improve the supply of portable drinking water.

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